

The Coupling Constants Series and the Strong Interaction – 8 Theory

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Abstract:

By analyzing the primorial coupling constants series and in particular, the electron being emitted from the quark configuration inside the hadronic structure, it is possible to analyze the coupling constant series in an angle that was not presented in the thesis. The analysis will emphasize the similarity of all coupling terms due to the existence of that invariant (3) element. Author will use the first and second representation of the primorial, i.e. net variations/curvature and spin.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30: 128: 850: 9254.. \quad (1.1)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); \quad V \geq 0 \quad (1.11)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \quad \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); \quad P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (1.12)$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.13)$$

$$\frac{e^2}{\hbar c} = \frac{1}{128} \quad (1.14)$$

$$\frac{e^2}{\hbar c} \rightarrow \frac{3^2}{128} \rightarrow \frac{8 + (1)}{128} = \frac{1}{128} \quad (1.15)$$

The main argument of this short essay is that it is possible to regard each higher coupling terms as the strong interaction being destabilized in ever-growing fermion formations. It's the electron that has so much significance in the coupling constants series. Back in the day, when author derived the coupling series, in the thesis he believed that each term would have unique destabilizer, but now it seems very clear that such an assumption is quite likely wrong and eventually will lead to complexity that is not needed. Another way to state it is that three is isomorphic to itself. What is varying is the size of the fermionic cluster and the magnitude of the net curvature. The shift in understanding manifested itself in toward the end of the thesis but still it is important to clarify to avoid confusion among readers. It is also possible to represent the coupling, as you already know, in the form of spin representations by setting it on the prime critical strip:

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} = 2N_1 + 1$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} = 2N_2 + 1$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} = 2N_3 + 1$$

To solidify the statements made in previous papers, the variance in that representation is the fermionic clusters, represented in the right of each term, and the net variation, or net curvature that is prime or one. The conclusion if one is correct is the electron is destabilizing larger and larger fermionic cluster yielding an infinite succession of net curvature on the manifold, which causes the endless process of clustering. One prefer that version, as it is simpler than to assume that each term would have a unique destabilizer. As the fermionic cluster gets much more massive in rate, the net curvature than becomes less significant, preciously the idea behind the principle of least variation.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)